

An Assessment of Post-Earthquake Issues in UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) Gastronomic Cities Gaziantep, Hatay and Şanlıurfa in Turkey

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Abstract

Destinations catering to tourists with specific gastronomic preferences or diverse motivations may experience occasional disruptions in the range of offerings available. This scenario may arise due to anthropogenic factors or natural phenomena that result in varying degrees of environmental degradation. The literature commonly reports that regions experiencing disasters such as wars, floods, epidemics, earthquakes, and hurricanes are susceptible to significant life, property, and economic losses. The seismic events that commenced on February 6th, 2023 and persist to the present have engendered a consequential phenomenon within the nation of Turkey. The present research has been conducted to examine the prospective impacts of the Gaziantep/Kahramanmaraş earthquakes of 2023 on Gastronomy tourism and to propose viable remedies for any associated issues. The study employed qualitative research methods, specifically observation and literature review, to gather data. The data that was acquired was subjected to analysis using the descriptive analysis methodology. In summary, based on the scientific literature review and contemporary scientific assessments of gastronomic tourism, it has been observed that this phenomenon can be leveraged as a tourism asset in the future, despite certain criticisms. Upon evaluating both domestic and foreign visual and printed media, it is apparent that there is a prevalence of favorable news regarding gastronomy tourism. Based on the literature and observational data gathered in the study, it is believed that the impact of the earthquake on the gastronomic tourism of Gaziantep, Hatay, and Şanlıurfa, which are recognized as UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) gastronomic cities, can be mitigated through appropriate measures. With multidimensional planning, the gastronomy of these cities is expected to emerge even stronger from the aftermath of the earthquake.

Keywords: UNESCO gastronomic cities, gastronomic tourism, earthquake in Turkey

1. Introduction

Tourism encompasses the act of individuals traveling from one location to another via various modes of transportation for the purpose of gaining diverse experiences, acquiring knowledge, and fulfilling other motivations. The primary determinant in this context is the inclination towards travel that individuals cultivate through their innate inquisitiveness and personal preferences. Gastronomic tourism can be pursued in conjunction with various travel motivations. The distinctive culinary traditions of the regions visited during travel, motivated by factors such as geography, environment, cultural heritage, spirituality, and well-being, are a compelling draw for tourists. In addition, certain individuals engage in gastronomic tourism as a means of discovering novel flavors and acquiring knowledge about diverse culinary customs. According to Toksöz et al. (2016), the attributes of tourist destinations serve as a motivating factor for individuals in their decision-making process and overall vacation experiences. Tourist destinations catering to gastronomic preferences or diverse motivations may experience occasional disruptions in the range of opportunities they provide. This scenario may manifest as a result of anthropogenic impacts or natural calamities that engender varying degrees of devastation. According to scholarly sources, regions that experience disasters such as wars, floods, epidemics, earthquakes, and hurricanes are generally associated with significant life, property, and economic losses. Various dimensions and aspects are negatively impacted by these processes, resulting in the loss of cities with significant tourism value. The ongoing seismic activity that commenced on February 6, 2023 has engendered a consequential phenomenon in Turkey. The earthquake that occurred on February 6, 2023 at 04:17 local time in Gaziantep's Şehitkamil District Sofalaca Village epicenter (Mw) was reported to be a highly destructive event with a magnitude of 7.7,

as per the findings published by TURKONFED. The earthquake's epicenter had a focal depth of approximately 5 kilometers and its effects were experienced across several regions including Southeastern Anatolia, Central Anatolia, Eastern Anatolia, and the Mediterranean. This seismic event is referred to by various designations, including Gaziantep-Kahramanmaraş or Southeastern Anatolia Earthquake. At 13:24 local time, a seismic event of moment magnitude (Mw) 7.5 transpired at the epicenter of Ekinözü District of Kahramanmaraş Province, resulting in significant damage and loss. The earthquake's epicenter had a focal depth of approximately 5 kilometers and its effects were observed in various regions including Southeastern Anatolia, Central Anatolia, Eastern Anatolia, and the Mediterranean. The seismic events in question are two major earthquakes that occurred at a distance of roughly 105 kilometers from each other, with a temporal separation of approximately 9 hours between their epicenters. Notably, no aftershocks were observed in the aftermath of these events. According to sources such as Turkonfed 2023 and MTA in 2023, it has been reported that a significant portion, specifically 15.7%, of Turkey's population resides in the provinces that have been designated as disaster areas, namely Kahramanmaraş, Hatay, Adiyaman, Gaziantep, Malatya, Kilis, Diyarbakır, Adana, Osmaniye, and Şanlıurfa.

1.1. Background

1.1.1. Gastronomy cities within the UNESCO network of creative cities

Since 2005, UNESCO, a global organization, has initiated the practice of conferring the 'City of Gastronomy' designation to urban centers that demonstrate exceptional culinary expertise. Urban centers must undergo a process of legalization by satisfying predetermined criteria, while also having the capacity to establish supplementary criteria of their own. The criteria for the application are as follows: the city or region must possess a

well-developed gastronomy, a quality gastronomy community comprising numerous local restaurants and chefs, utilization of traditional interior materials in traditional kitchens, preservation of local knowledge despite industrial and technological advancements, existence of culinary practices and methods, and the growth of traditional food and beverage industry and traditional food sales areas. UNESCO (2021) has identified several distinct criteria that are specific to cities. These include the implementation of gastronomic festivals, competitions, and other comprehensive tourism activities, as well as the promotion of environmentally sustainable local products. The city has been designated as a member of the UNESCO Creative Cities Network for its contributions to various artistic fields, including music, cinema, literature, and gastronomy. Similar to other cities known for their creativity, this title highlights the importance of creativity. The prevalence of food globalization is diminishing the influence of regional delicacies. Conversely, it is imperative to provide backing and enhancement for the indigenous gastronomic customs of urban areas and to impart cultural heritage to forthcoming cohorts (Agamirova, 2014). The present scenario can be elucidated by the definition attributed to the term "gastronomy city" as per the literature. The interplay of historical, geographical, and climatic factors has given rise to a diverse array of regional cuisines across the globe, characterized by their richness and vibrancy. The designation of "City of Gastronomy" is conferred to underscore the abundance of culinary offerings, with a particular emphasis on regional provenance (Xiomin, 2004). Over time, the designation of a city as a gastronomic hub has become increasingly enriched and fortified in its purpose. Nevertheless, this designation is conferred irrespective of the dimensions, financial system, or populace of the urban center. Small and medium-sized cities have become recognized as creative cities by

earning the designation of gastronomy city. Metropolitan areas that are renowned for their culinary expertise require strategic plans for local growth and global backing, with a focus on cultural industries and innovative practices. Cities that satisfy specific criteria, such as possessing a diverse local cuisine and utilizing conventional ingredients and culinary methods, are designated as 'Gastronomy Cities' on a global scale (Güler et al., 2017). The designation of a city as a gastronomic hub not only facilitates its promotional efforts, but also enhances its visibility under this legally protected label (Akdu and Akdu, 2018). In October 2004, UNESCO introduced the "UNESCO Creative Cities Network" program, as reported by Popescu and Corboş (2012). The objective of this endeavor is to enhance collaboration via assistance, as stated by UNESCO (2021). The Creative Cities Network is comprised of seven distinct networks, each with a specific theme such as Handcrafts and Folk Art, Music, Gastronomy, Design, Film, Literature, and Media Arts. The primary aim of these networks is to enhance the socioeconomic and cultural growth of cities, as noted by various scholars (Popescu et al., 2012; Leng et al., 2014; Kostanski et al., 2014). The UNESCO Creative Cities Network encompasses a total of 118 cities hailing from 54 different countries across the globe. It is noteworthy that the network comprises 809 members. According to Kostanski et al. (2014), the longevity and consistency of cities are contingent upon their ability to fulfill the objectives of their respective networks and maintain their designation as such.

2. Materials and Methods

The present study aims to examine the potential impacts of the earthquakes that occurred in Gaziantep/Kahramanmaraş on February 6, 2023, on the domain of Gastronomy tourism. Additionally, the study seeks to provide viable solutions to any issues that may arise as a result of the aforementioned seismic events. The study focuses on the provinces of Gaziantep,

Hatay, and Şanlıurfa, which hold significant importance in Turkey's gastronomic tourism industry. The study utilized qualitative research methods such as observation and literature review to gather data. Qualitative research is a methodology that involves the use of qualitative data collection techniques, such as observation, document analysis, and interviews, to uncover events and perceptions in a realistic and comprehensive manner within a natural setting. This approach follows a qualitative process and is well-documented in the literature (Cohen et al., 2007; Ritchie et al., 2003).

3. Result

3.1. Tourism and gastronomy

The word gastronomy is etymologically derived from the combination of the Greek words “gatros”, “stomach” and “nomos”, “law, rule” (Yılmaz, 2017; Tütüncü, 2019). However, different disciplines reflect the definition of gastronomy by putting their own perspectives in focus. For this reason, it is possible to encounter many definitions about gastronomy. For this reason, it is not easy to define the concept of gastronomy, and it can be said that the definition of gastronomy in general terms is expressed by revealing the scientific and artistic aspects of a quality and delicious food or beverage (Gillespie, 2001). Gastronomy tourism is a type of tourism in which tourists participate in providing information on the stages from the preparation of food and beverages to the presentation of foods and drinks (Kivela et al., 2006; Hall et al., 2001). The desire of tourists to experience local tastes in destinations and accommodations has paved the ground for the development of gastronomic tourism. Gastronomy tourism belongs to a subcategory of cultural tourism. Gastronomy is seen as an expression of culture. (Manolaa et al., 2020). Gastronomy tourism enables the acquisition of information about a particular place, the consumption of food and beverages, resulting in a better understanding of local traditions and the

culture of that place There are many sub-titles and activities of gastronomy tourism (Küçükkömürler et al., 2019). These are; Food types such as beverage tourism, chocolate tourism and cheese tourism (Güzel-Sahin and Ünver, 2015), edible herbs (Pehlivan, 2023) (Quan and Wang, 2004),

- Visits to the production site (factory), visit the peasant markets, visit the bond or fruit garden,
- Eating and drinking in restaurants, cafes, etc.
- Workshops and conferences,
- Applications in rural areas (Smith and Costello, 2009; Povey, 2011),
- Festivals (Dönmez and Pehlivan, 2022)
- Spices and olive oil, ice cream, medicinal aromatic plants, gastronomy and cooking museums (Gökçe et al., 2017; Çavdırılı and Adan, 2020; Çekal et al., 2022; Gül, 2022), can be used as a tourist vehicle in this context.

3.2. Gastronomy cities and gastronomic characteristics: Gaziantep, Hatay and Şanlıurfa

The cities of Gaziantep, Hatay, and Şanlıurfa have been designated as gastronomy cities due to their prominent culinary characteristics. These distinguishing features have contributed to their recognition as such. The subsequent section presents the distinctive features of the pertinent cities, organized under individual headings and described in detail. The sequence of cities included is determined based on the order of their titular hierarchy in Turkey:

3.2.1. Gaziantep

Gastronomy city Gaziantep is a special and worth seeing city with unique eating and drinking behaviors. The seasonal preparations for eating drinks contain many local details. This topic has attracted the attention of many scientific researchers (Birecikligil, 2007; Dönmez et al., 2019; Fidan et al., 2019, Shenol et al., 2021). In many places in Turkey and the world, these products have been named and ordered

from Gaziantep. Gaziantep is also the leading province in Turkey with the largest gastronomic portfolio in terms of geographically marked products. This includes 99 products and 1 traditional product registered by the Turkish Patent and Trademark Authority. (Gaziantep Belediyesi, 2022). However, in Gaziantep, the Sahre culture (the habit of picnicing on Sundays) is another culinary value worth considering, the fact that the city's distinctive dishes can be practically made with butchers in every bakery of the city, and have practical food options such as nuts. Various scientific studies have aimed to determine the typologies of tourists visiting Gaziantep restaurants. According to the data obtained in this scope, tourists who like to eat and drink are divided into five themes: curious people, farmers, artists, socialists and those who care about healthy eating. For example, it has been seen that the expectations of tourists who like to eat and drink curiously in their travel motivations are to learn food-sweetened recipes and spices used in food, to become the foundation for the historical processes of food and the cooking stages, and to taste high-paid dishes (Kırıcı et al., 2023). Simşek et al. (2018) stated that the typologies of tourists visiting Gaziantep are those who care about food, those who aim to learn, organicists, farmers and innovators. Gaziantep is a city renowned for its gastronomic offerings, boasting an extensive culinary culture characterized by a diverse array of high-quality products. Gaziantep was awarded the UNESCO gastronomy city label in 2015, owing to its rich culinary heritage. In general, Gaziantep is known for its culinary tradition that features meat, oil, piquant spices, and copious amounts of tomato paste. The practice of blending tomato and pepper paste is a common culinary technique. Apart from lamb, mutton is extensively utilized in culinary preparations. All meals are prepared using either natural butter or oil. Sumac is widely utilized in the region for various culinary purposes such as

enhancing the flavor of salads, meals, and piyaz. Additionally, it is commonly used in combination with sour cream and pomegranate molasses to add a touch of sweetness to the dish. Spices such as hyssop, black pepper, haspir, thyme, sesame, mahaleb, red pepper, saffron, tarragon, cinnamon, and sumac are commonly favored. Various herbs and spices are utilized in culinary practices to enhance the flavor and aroma of dishes. For instance, sesame is incorporated in the production of yoghurt dishes and pastries, while saffron is commonly used in pastry making. Tarragon is a popular ingredient in rice varieties, desserts, and pastries, whereas sumac is utilized in stuffed meats, salads, and piyaz. Additionally, hashish is employed in the preparation of meatballs and soups, as reported by Sabbağ (2015). The Turkish Patent and Trademark Office, which operates under the Ministry of Industry and Technology, has categorized the product under its traditional name and sign of origin, as well as its original name. The aforementioned classes encompass a range of product groups, including soft drinks, alcoholic beverages, confectionery and chocolate products, ice creams, bakery products, fruit and vegetable spreads, oils, cheeses, meals, soups, condiments, and pastry products (Türkpatent, 2021).

3.2.2. Hatay

Hatay tables exhibit a diverse range of classifications, including the guest table, holiday table, family table, Ramadan table, hammam table, wedding table, entertainment-banquet table, and votive table. The food presentations prominently showcase the hallmark hospitality of the Mediterranean populace. According to Aytekin (2009), ceremonial meals, believed to have been influenced by Roman culture, involve prolonged periods of dining at the table and culminate in musical and entertainment performances. According to Şahin (2012), the predominant characteristic of Hatay cuisine is its utilization of spices, which are employed extensively in dishes for both flavoring and

embellishment purposes. Thyme, cumin, fennel seeds, black pepper, cloves, black cumin, and cinnamon are widely utilized in culinary applications. The olfactory stimuli of fragrances have the ability to create a lasting impression in individuals' memory. There is a prevailing notion that the aromas emanating from culinary preparations serve as a sensory cue for the corresponding flavors, thereby endowing spices with a mnemonic function. According to Cömert (2014), the utilization of spices constitutes the foundation of the culinary creations in Hatay cuisine. The region of Hatay is known for its distinctive culinary offerings, including Antakya Paper Kebab, Antakya Kunefe, Antakya Surku, Salted Yoghurt, Antakya Moldy Surku, and various products that bear a geographical indication. The Dörtyol mandarin is a product that bears the mark of origin.

3.2.3. Şanlıurfa

The cuisine of Şanlıurfa boasts a diverse selection of local foods and beverages, which is in line with the wide range of culinary offerings found in Turkish cuisine. The culinary tradition of Şanlıurfa has been shaped by the amalgamation of numerous civilizations. The culinary synthesis of Şanlıurfa comprises a blend of various cultural influences, including Turkish, Arab, Syriac, Armenian, Kurdish, Yazidi, and others. The entity in question encompasses the entirety of various ethnicities and their corresponding cultural practices. The significant potential for gastronomy tourism in Şanlıurfa is evidenced by the presence of businesses and institutions that reflect the rich culinary culture of the region. The Turkish Patent and Trademark Office has granted geographical indication to 33 products, thereby acknowledging their potential. Upon analyzing this significant potential through the lens of the gastronomic identity model, as categorized by Hjalager (2002) into local, horizontal, vertical, and cross-development gastronomic tourism products, the utilization of isot, a crucial gastronomic product originating from Şanlıurfa, in

venues such as historical bazaars, local product markets, and directly in tourism, represents the initial archetype of the model. This can be exemplified as a manifestation of the local development phase, which denotes the specific stage of regional growth. The horizontal development stage can be likened to the provision of uncooked meatballs to patrons in the food and beverage industry. During the vertical development stage, the integration of gastronomic products with other tourism offerings is a common practice. This can be observed through various initiatives, such as showcasing local culinary products during the sira night and hosting gastronomy festivals. It can be argued that Şanlıurfa falls short in terms of teaching and implementing the production processes of the products that are fundamental to cross-development, the final stage of the model. According to Hjalager's gastronomic identity model, Şanlıurfa can be classified as being in the vertical development stage within this particular context.

3.3. The role of tourism in economic development and the economic effects of disasters on tourism

3.3.1 The role of tourism in economic development

Touristic attraction centers are important sources of income for the provinces where they are located and therefore for the country. For this reason, tourism, which is known for its high multiplier effect on the economy, is accepted as an ideal development tool because it creates a revival in the direct and indirect sectors. Since the second half of the 20th century, the tourism industry has become one of the fastest developing and growing economies in the world economy (Yiğit et al., 2018). Thanks to tourism, tourists benefit from the economic level of the country and people they travel to by spending in the places they go, and they carry out monetary transfer between countries with international tourism activities. In addition to the mentioned

economic effects, the social, political, etc. effects of the tourism sector. It is possible to see its positive effects in many fields. Therefore, it is seen that the tourism sector is extremely important in both developed and developing countries (Bingöl et al., 2020). Gastronomic tourism has a special importance in the tourism sector. Yiğit et al. (2018) states that it is predicted that “gastronomy tourism” will be the type of tourism that guides the world economy for 2020 and beyond. Gastronomic products have an important place in tourism revenues. In addition, these products increase local product consumption, provide income to the local economy and support local production. Incomes to be obtained from local economic development fulfill an important function in the fight against income inequality as well as having an effect on growth and development. According to the report prepared by the EU; It is stated that member and candidate countries make great contributions to the national economies in terms of added value, employment and number of enterprises in terms of gastronomic tourism. The contribution of the accommodation and gastronomy sector to the national economy is 30% and 70%, respectively. These data reveal the importance of gastronomic tourism (European Commission, 2014).

3.3.2. Economic effects of disasters on tourism

Disasters have occurred in every period of history. Disasters may be of natural origin such as landslides, floods, earthquakes, or they may occur due to anthropogenic causes such as terrorism, plane crash and fire. Disasters that cannot be determined exactly when, where and in what form they will occur have similar effects in terms of their results. These effects can cause economic losses, especially physical losses, and social psychological destruction (Altun, 2018). Natural disasters generally affect the country in which they are experienced in many ways, and the source of this effect may also be caused by some global events.

For example; In the 2003-2021 period, the number of foreign visitors to Turkey has fluctuated. Bird flu (2006), the global economic crisis in the USA (2008), swine flu (2009-2010), Ebola (2013), MERS (2015) and Covid-19 (2019) epidemics were effective in this fluctuating course. However, the biggest fluctuation experienced is the Covid-19 (-69.48%) pandemic, which seriously affected all other countries (Şen et al., 2015; Çeti et al., 2019; Piret et al., 2021; Novelli et al., 2018; Çavuşgil et al., 2020). All these negative environmental conditions, inevitably, negatively affect the tourism of the region where it takes place. This decline in tourism has negative repercussions on the country's economy. Türkiye is exposed to many disasters due to its geopolitical position. These are disasters such as earthquakes, landslides, floods and avalanches (Şahin et al., 2016). According to the statistical distribution of disasters in Turkey, 58% of disaster victims are those affected by earthquakes. Earthquake events have occurred in the world and in Turkey in the past and have been dealt with in many studies with their economic dimension. According to some of these studies; earthquakes (and natural disasters in general) have significant negative effects on economic growth (Barro et al., 2003; Raddatz, 2009). Apart from the first-degree financial losses among these negative effects, some studies in recent years emphasize that there may be potential spillover effects across the economy through trade links and supply chains (The et al., 2011; Ruta et al., 2021). However, contrary to the aforementioned negative opinions, some researchers state that disasters such as earthquakes have mild or even positive effects on growth (Albala-Bertrand, 1993; Barone et al., 2014, Caselli et al., 2004, Loayza et al., 2012, Porcelli et al., 2019, Skidmore et al., 2002). Economic effects of earthquakes; pre-earthquake economic conditions depend on the destruction they cause and the ability to rebuild the resources of the economy

(Hallegatte et al., 2022). Countries with poor economies, low government spending and weak institutions are more likely to be affected by the negative effects of earthquakes on growth (Cavallo et al., 2013; DuRose, 2023; Lackner, 2018; Noy, 2009; Toya et al., 2007). These negative effects especially affect poor people in societies with high domestic inequalities (Colmer, 2021). However, approximately 1 million 548 thousand people lost their lives due to earthquakes in the 20th century in the world. When it comes to the damages of disasters, although death, physical losses and injuries come to mind first, important social, economic and psychological consequences have emerged (Altun, 2018). Letukas et al. (2008) report that the tsunami and earthquake that occurred on the coast of Sumatra, Indonesia, on December 26, 2004, caused both short-term social changes during the disaster and long-term social changes due to the changes in political structures and economy. Turkey is located in the 1st degree earthquake zone (Altun, 2018), where 98% of its population and 93% of its territory are under the influence of various degrees of earthquakes (Şahin et al., 2016). Therefore, when we look at the earthquake history of Turkey, it is not surprising to encounter earthquakes of different intensities in different regions. The economic effects of earthquakes in Turkey between 1980 and 2014 were examined by Şahin et al. (2016). As a result, it was determined that the earthquakes in Turkey caused great losses in the country's economy (Şahin et al., 2016). In order to minimize these losses, it has been suggested to create disaster awareness throughout the country, to analyze disasters according to regions, to prepare before disasters, to raise awareness of people of all ages within the scope of damage reduction, to take necessary precautions during post-disaster recovery and rebuilding phases. Land (2019) occurred on 27.06.1998 around Adana-Ceyhan. He states that as a result of the 6.3-magnitude earthquake and numerous aftershocks, 145 loss of life, more

than 1500 injured and substantial material damage occurred, 1124 buildings were destroyed in the earthquake, and 10252 buildings were uninhabitable. He stated that the losses that first attracted the attention of the public and public institutions as a result of this earthquake were life and economic losses, but besides all these losses, the social texture, population composition and employment opportunities of the region were also turned upside down by the earthquake (Kara, 2019). The Marmara earthquake that took place on 17.08.1999, on the other hand, caused a much greater social reaction and social anxiety environment among the earthquakes in Turkey. This is due to the fact that it takes place in a region like Marmara where industrialization and urbanization are fast and intense (Kolukırık et al., 2009). Although the earthquake experienced on February 6, 2023 is larger than the Marmara earthquake in terms of magnitude, experts who compare these two important earthquakes make the following statements (Aksoy et al., 2023); The 1999 earthquake in Turkey was worse than the earthquake in 2023. Although of low severity, it occurred in the industrial center of the country. The four regions worst affected by the 1999 earthquake (Kocaeli, Sakarya, Bolu and Yalova) comprise about 4% of the country's population. But these are the provinces that have important economic links with the rest of the country, including Istanbul and Bursa, and are directly responsible for around 7% of GDP and 14% of industry added value. As a result, significant damage has occurred to energy, transport and communications infrastructure in the wider region. The regions that experienced major disruptions due to the earthquake together account for 35% of GDP and half of industrial production. The initial economic slowdown reflects the deterioration of physical capital, workforce, supply chains, inventory loss and low investment in the immediate aftermath of the earthquake. In this process, many small businesses went bankrupt because they did not have

earthquake insurance. This has a knock-on effect on the banking sector, which saw a sharp increase in non-performing loans prior to the 2001 financial crisis (Bibbee et al., 2000). On the other hand, the reconstruction activities carried out after the earthquake accelerated the growth of the country in 2000. Unlike 1999, the 2023 earthquake occurred earlier in the year. As a result, the restructuring effect will largely occur in the same calendar year, significantly offsetting the negative impact of earthquake-related disruptions on GDP. In addition, due to the widespread use of earthquake insurance compared to 1999, its impact on the banking sector is expected to be more limited. The overall impact of the 2023 earthquakes on economic growth is likely to be less than one percent of output (GDP) in 2023, against the backdrop of significant increases in government spending. However, the results of these estimates are not yet clear. The International Money Fund believes that the last 7.8 earthquakes will do less damage to the economy than the 7.6 earthquakes in 1999. Liam Peach, senior emerging markets economist at Capital Economics in London, "believes that economic activity can quickly recover after the earthquake any impact this quarter will be offset." The Central Bank of Türkiye also declared that they believe that the Turkish economy will not be affected in the medium term. If we look at the export figures of the 10 provinces in the Disaster Region, these provinces realize 8.7 percent of the total exports. While more than half of this 19.76 billion dollars export in 2022 was realized in Gaziantep with 10.52 billion dollars, Hatay 3.56, Adana 3 and Kahramanmaraş exported 1.46 billion dollars. Pulses, cereals, steel, oilseeds and their products, etc. agricultural products; ready-made garments, textiles and raw materials are the leading export items (TURKONFED, 2023). Aksoy et al. (2023) The views of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development on the subject; "He believes that Turkey could lose up to 1% of its GDP. Growth was predicted

as 3.5% for Türkiye, now it has decreased to 3%. As Turkey is the leading supplier of many fruits, including apricots, it could have a ripple effect on the world economy. Besides agriculture and industrial production, tourism is also an important part. It is expected that this sector will also take a big hit, as the Turkish economy is no longer accessible to many popular tourist destinations. As it can be seen, there are positive views on the subject as well as some concerns.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

In this study, the potential effects of the 2023 Gaziantep/Kahramanmaraş earthquakes on Gastronomy tourism were investigated. Gaziantep, Hatay and Urfa provinces, which have a very important place in Turkey in terms of gastronomic tourism, constitute the research area in the study. In the research, data obtained through observation and literature review, one of the qualitative research techniques, were collected. The obtained data were analyzed using descriptive analysis method. The study is limited to the observations of the researcher, since the earthquake event and its effects continue throughout the research and the researcher is actively residing in the research area people live. The interview technique could not be used due to various problems caused by the panic situation. In the literature review, scientific literature sources, data from current domestic and foreign news sites were used. The data obtained in the study are presented by dividing the titles. In conclusion; The 2023 Gaziantep/Kahramanmaraş earthquakes represent a period in which such frequent and long-lasting earthquakes have not been experienced together before, which caused 10 provinces and Sivas/Gürün district to be declared as disaster areas in Turkey. In the earthquakes that occurred, the provinces within the disaster area were affected by the disaster in various forms and sizes. Gaziantep, Turkey's first gastronomic city, is also located in the disaster area. Moreover, this province is one of the important industrial cities of the region. It is

also one of the most important provinces of Turkey in terms of gastronomy tourism. The earthquakes experienced caused significant losses in the İslahiye and Nurdağı districts of Gaziantep. However, the number of destroyed buildings in the city center is very low. Although improvement works continue at the transportation point of the province, there is no interruption in transportation. Local people have turned to vineyard houses or villages in order to stay away from high-rise buildings. Although some of the people go out of the city, the return has accelerated with the opening of the schools. According to the scientific literature review and current scientific evaluations on gastronomic tourism, criticisms are made that this process can be turned into an advantage in terms of tourism in the following periods. When the news in the domestic and foreign visual/printed media is evaluated, there are positive news for gastronomy tourism. However, some organizations abroad state that tourism may be adversely affected by the process in general. According to the literature and observational data obtained in the study, it is thought that the effects of the earthquake in Gaziantep, Hatay and Şanlıurfa gastronomy tourism can be overcome by taking the right steps, and the gastronomy in the provinces will come out stronger from the process, provided that the planning of the current situation is multidimensional. Regarding the 2023 Gaziantep/Kahramanmaraş earthquakes, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development stated that “As many popular touristic spots are no longer accessible, the tourism sector and therefore the Turkish economy is expected to suffer a major blow” (Aksoy et al., 2023). The researcher went to İslahiye and Nurdağı, the districts of Gaziantep, in the week of the earthquake, to offer condolences and help to his relatives and friends living in the disaster area. The observations here are as follows; “In the first days of the disaster, it was seen that the roads were mostly open in İslahiye and Nurdağı districts and there was no

danger related to the road condition, the collapsed and cracked places on the roads were intervened and road improvement works were continuing for the future processes. However, in the Nurdağı tunnels and viaducts area of the Tarsus-Adana-Gaziantep (TAG) Highway, which makes a significant contribution to the inter-provincial connection of these two districts and Kahramanmaraş, Gaziantep, Adıyaman Malatya and Şanlıurfa, there are serious problems at the first stage and it takes time to resolve this problem is known to have. In addition to all these conditions, in addition to the aid from all over the country and from abroad, our people in the region have embraced each other and tried to heal the wounds together. Disaster survivors try to help those around them by putting their own pain and suffering aside. We all experience together that this process binds us together more.” At this point, although the earthquake process first brought with it some difficulties, there does not seem to be an important situation that will cause injuries to these sectors in Gaziantep, Hatay and Şanlıurfa for gastronomy and other tourism activities. However, considering the extent of the disaster, it should be known that almost every sector of Gaziantep and the gastronomy area, which is the prominent area of the province, also have lessons to be learned from these earthquakes. The following discourse provides a comprehensive assessment of the gastronomy tourism in Gaziantep, Hatay, and Şanlıurfa, along with potential measures that can be implemented to enhance this domain. Following seismic activity, it is common for members of the general populace to discover commercial establishments such as markets and food vendors situated beneath high-rise structures. It avoids locations and exhibits a preference for single-level structures. The proposed approach involves relocating brand businesses that play a significant role in Gaziantep's gastronomic tourism to single or double-storey establishments within the city. This measure is expected to

instill confidence among both local residents and international visitors. The relocation of these enterprises from high-rise structures to urban centers or suburban regions is an additional aspect that warrants consideration. The regions that were deemed secure for habitation by the indigenous populace have now been developed into residences with low-floor architecture. In this procedure, particularly in the edifices designated as Mass Housing Administration edifices, which were constructed under the supervision and financing of the government, the attribute of "greater robustness" instills assurance in the populace. The significance of the state's involvement in the construction and regulation processes is paramount in the context of recuperation. The orientation of food businesses should be ascertained with respect to these areas, and relevant businesses ought to be duly notified. Furthermore, it is imperative to provide multidimensional support to enterprises engaged in gastronomy tourism, based on land classification, in order to guide them towards suitable areas and ensure compliance with established safety standards. The occurrence of an earthquake is classified as one of the various types of natural disasters. The contemporary issue of ecological degradation pertains to the depletion of natural resources such as water and soil, as well as the challenge of ensuring sustainable energy sources and food production. It is imperative to promptly implement measures to address these requirements. The incorporation of sustainable urban planning should be prioritized in the redevelopment initiatives intended for urban regions in the aftermath of seismic events. The integration of urban

agriculture into the framework of sustainable urban planning may be a viable option for the cities of Gaziantep, Hatay, and Şanlıurfa. Urban agriculture is a practice that has been observed to have several benefits. These benefits include contributing to urban ecology, creating new food sources, raising ecological awareness among the populace, reducing food access inequality, promoting psychological recovery, and fostering social cohesion. Furthermore, upon the demolition of the significantly or moderately impaired edifices situated in the urban hub, these zones can be repurposed for culinary tourism. Gastronomy enterprises have the option to allocate a portion of their suppliers towards these regions for food production. These regions provide an opportunity for both domestic and international tourists to witness the entire process of food production, from its inception to the final presentation on the plate. The provision of support necessary for the implementation of this system by enterprises may be facilitated through collaboration between local government and academic institutions. The present study employed a literature review approach, utilizing scientific literature sources as well as data obtained from current domestic and foreign news sites. The data that was acquired was subjected to analysis using the descriptive analysis methodology. The study employed a methodology of utilizing gastronomy-tourism, disaster-earthquake-tourism, disaster-earthquake-economy, and 2023 Turkey earthquake (in both Turkish and English languages) as keywords to generate the titles of the findings. Table 1 presents the obtained results.

Table 1. The codes used in the research and the data titles created.

Codes	The topic of discussion pertains to the headers of data
Tourism Gastronomy Gaziantep Hatay Şanlıurfa Gastronomy Tourism Economy Gastronomy Disaster Earthquake 2023 Turkey earthquake	Tourism and Gastronomy Gastronomy cities and gastronomic characteristics: Gaziantep, Hatay and Şanlıurfa The Role of Tourism in Economic Development and the Economic Effects of Disasters on Tourism

This study makes a valuable contribution to the existing literature by addressing the contemporary issue of earthquakes and their significant impact on tourism. Furthermore, the inclusion of Gaziantep, Hatay, and Şanlıurfa as focal points for gastronomy tourism lends significant weight to the study. These cities are renowned for their culinary offerings and thus enhance the study's significance.

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